

THE MODERATING ROLE OF PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LEARNED RESOURCEFULNESS AND WORK STRESS IN HOTEL BUSINESSES: THE CASE OF CAPPADOCIA

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of learned resourcefulness and the dimensions of perceived social support on work stress and whether there is a moderating role of the dimensions of perceived social support in the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress in hotel businesses. With this purpose, judgmental sampling method was preferred as the sampling method in this study and data were collected from the employees of four- and five-star hotels in Cappadocia through questionnaires. Data were examined with simple and multiple linear regression and hierarchical regression analyses. Based on the results of the study, a negative effect of both learned resourcefulness and the "family" dimension of perceived social support on work stress was discovered; but the effects of "friend" and "significant other" dimensions on work stress were insignificant. In addition, another result was that the "family" dimension of perceived social support played a moderating role in the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress. Finally, recommendations were made based on the findings.

Keywords: Hotel businesses; Learned resourcefulness; Perceived social support; Work stress; Cappadocia region.

O PAPEL DA ORGANIZAÇÃO DO APOIO SOCIAL RECEBIDO NA RELAÇÃO DE FORTEZA E STRESS LABORAL APRENDIDO NAS EMPRESAS HOTELEIRAS: EXEMPLO DA CAPADÓCIA

Resumo

O objetivo deste estudo é determinar o impacto da forteza e do apoio social percebido nas empresas hoteleiras sobre o stress do trabalho e se as dimensões do apoio social percebidas na relação entre a força aprendida e o stress do trabalho têm um papel regulador. Neste âmbito, o método de amostragem judicial foi preferido na investigação e os dados foram recolhidos com a ajuda da técnica de levantamento aplicada aos funcionários de hotéis de quatro e cinco estrelas da região da Capadócia. Os dados foram testados com uma regressão simples e multi-linear e uma análise hierárquica de regressão. A força e o apoio social percebidos como resultado da investigação têm um impacto negativo no stress do trabalho; Foi revelado que as dimensões dos "amigos" e dos "outros" não têm qualquer efeito significativo no stress do trabalho. Concluiu-se ainda que a dimensão "familiar" do apoio social percebido desempenha um papel regulador na relação entre a força aprendida e o stress do trabalho. Por último, os resultados dos resultados foram avaliados e foram feitas recomendações.

Palavras-chave: Empresas de hotéis; Aprendeu força; Percepção de apoio social; Stress do trabalho; Região da Capadócia.

EL PAPEL MODERADOR DEL APOYO SOCIAL PERCIBIDO EN LA RELACIÓN ENTRE LA COMPETENCIA APRENDIDA Y EL ESTRÉS LABORAL EN LOS ESTABLECIMIENTOS HOTELEROS: EL CASO DE CAPADOCIA

Resumen

El propósito de este estudio es determinar la influencia de la competencia aprendida y el apoyo social percibido en el estrés laboral y si las dimensiones del apoyo social percibido tienen un papel moderador en la relación entre la competencia aprendida y el estrés laboral en los establecimientos hoteleros. Con este propósito, se prefirió el método de muestreo por juicio en este estudio y se recogieron los datos mediante cuestionarios aplicados a los empleados que trabajan en los hoteles de cuatro ó cinco estrellas en Capadocia. Se examinaron los datos en el análisis de regresión lineal simple y múltiple y de regresión jerárquica. Como resultado del estudio, se descubrió que tenían una influencia negativa la competencia aprendida y la dimensión "familia" del apoyo social percibido en el estrés laboral; pero no tenían una influencia significativa las dimensiones "amigo" y "otros significativos" en el estrés laboral. Además, fue obtenido otro resultado que la dimensión "familia" del apoyo social percibido desempeñó un papel regulador en la relación entre la competencia aprendida y el estrés laboral. Por último, se dieron recomendaciones según las conclusiones.

Palabras clave: Establecimientos hoteleros; Competencia aprendida; Apoyo social percibido; Estrés laboral; Región de Capadocia.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism is now considered one of the world's largest industries (D'Mello et al., 2016; Baks & Parida, 2020) and stress is considered as one of the biggest problems likely to be encountered in hotel businesses recently. Hotel employees are supposed to cope with many problems such as low motivation, declined success drive, decreased productivity and performance, reduced organisational loyalty, alienating from work, not reaching goals set by organisation due to their not avoiding stress factors in work life and being exposed to overstress.

In this sense, learned resourcefulness concept has emerged as an assisting personal trait in coping with stressful situations efficiently (Ward-Miller et al., 2019; Keskin, 2020; Wen et al., 2021). Therefore, it is thought that increasing learned resourcefulness levels for the purpose of keeping stress at optimum level and the resistance of human resource against stressful situations will positively affect hotel businesses.

One another coping strategy utilized in coping with stress sources is the perceived social support concept. In consequence of the literature survey, it is seen that social support which has lately become one of the most investigated concepts along with stress concept has mitigated stress and played a significant role in individual's recovery from negative effects caused by stress (Frison & Eggermont, 2016).

Therefore, social support has recently received intensive attention and it satisfies an individual's physical, psychological, and cognitive needs (Chang et al., 2021). Today, human capital has gained importance due to the high competition in the tourism sector (Yilmazer et al., 2020; Onat et al., 2021).

Also, hospitality sector is a service sector and in this sector, human is both the provider and recipient of the service. Hence that hotel employees have the ability of learned resourcefulness and they receive external support to relieve them enables them to keep away from stress a bit and helps them to provide better service.

Though learned resourcefulness, perceived social support and work stress terms examined in the study are handled one by one in various fields, a study in which these variables were used altogether in tourism field has not been encountered.

Thereby, in this study it is aimed to reveal whether learned resourcefulness of hotel employees and perceived social support have an effect on lessening work stress and whether the dimensions of perceived social support play a moderating role in the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Learned Resourcefulness

Learned resourcefulness is defined as overall of coping stress, faith, ability and self control behaviors (Rosenbaum, 1990). According to Meichenbaum (1977), exhibiting clear behaviors in order to maintain control against stressful and challenging events and at the same time to be able to deal with internal stress sources effectively means learned resourcefulness.

While Dağ (1992) defines learned resourcefulness as the skill that individuals possess to rescue themselves successfully from the position they face in the stressful state, Rachman (1990) describes learned resourcefulness as a person's skill to use their individual and social sources to be able to cope with problems efficiently.

In the studies conducted, individuals with high learned resourcefulness were able to use their different skills to reduce the anxiety which could affect their performance, the ones with low learned resourcefulness were overwhelmed by their anxiety (Rosenbaum & Jaffe, 1983).

Further, individuals with high learned resourcefulness can deal with pain better (Rosenbaum, 1980b); can control themselves better (Frankel & Merbaum, 1982; Martin & Kennett, 2018); can reduce aggressive behaviour (Ronen & Rosenbaum, 2009); can exhibit better skills (Rosenbaum & Rolnick, 1983; Fang et al., 2021); can resist learned helplessness better (Rosenbaum & Ben-Ari, 1985; Dağ, 1992) can quit bad habits more easily (Rosenbaum, 1990; Bulut & Zeren, 2021); can use their abilities better to delay immediate gratification (Rosenbaum & Ben-Ari Smira, 1986; Guloglu & Aydın, 2007); are less influenced by stress sources and manage depression better (Huang & Guo, 2009; Chung et al, 2012; Ngai & Chan, 2012; Wright & Richmond Mynett 2019; Keskin, 2020; Chen et al., 2021; Wen et al., 2021).

2.2 Perceived Social Support

Social support concept, the most researched psycho-social source lately (Thoits, 1995), is a term based upon social change theory and the one involving various dimensions of the support individuals need (Lu & Hampton, 2017).

According to Cobb (1976), social support means that individuals know they are loved, respected, appreciated and they belong to a social net in which they are responsible for each other. With a similar definition, Sarason et al., (1983) define social support as the condition in which people who care love and trust them exist.

Shumaker & Brownell (1984) also state social support as the exchange of sources taking place between at least two people as recipient and providing intended to enhance the well-being of the recipient. When people are asked how they survived from the crisis moment and stressful situation, they think the key to this is the natural helpers such as family members and friends (Croog et al., 1972). Consequently, social support could be considered as the source in coping with stressors (Lazarus, 1993; Thoits, 1995).

2.3 Work Stress

The happenings of worklife and the effects of the environment have caused the stress to be lived at various levels day after day. Therefore, the concept of work stress has recently become one of the concepts which needs to be considered important by both employees and administrators (Katić et al., 2019).

Work stress is the reaction of people when faced with work demands incompatible with their knowledge, abilities and pressures they can not overcome (World Health Organization, 2020).

Work stress causes employees to display dysfunctional behaviors and is an emotional state leading to a reaction shown against the imbalance between their coping skills and work demand. In fact, work stress emerges when dealing with task, responsibility and other situations which cause pressure related to work and it inevitable that employees feel challenge, tension, anxiety and depression while doing it (Kang et al., 2021).

The source of stress varies from person to person and the reasons for stress have been investigated by many researchers (Kusuma, 2018; Zhu et al., 2020).

Based on these approaches, Aydın (2004) has summarized the reasons for work stress in hotel businesses as the stress causes resulted from organisational political sources, organisational structure sources, physical conditions in the workplace, type of work and the relations between people in the organisation. Thus, it is considered that the detailed investigation of these variations is highly significant in terms of providing better service to clients and increasing competition in tourism businesses.

3 METHODOLOGY

Within the study scope, the following hypotheses are suggested and assessed in line with analyses.

H1: Learned resourcefulness has a negative effect on work stress.

H2a: The “family” dimension of perceived social support has a negative effect on work stress.

H2b: The “friend” dimension of perceived social support has a negative effect on work stress.

H2c: The “significant other” dimension of perceived social support has a negative effect on work stress.

H3a: The “family” dimension of social support in the relation of learned resourcefulness and work stress has a moderating role.

H3b: The “friend” dimension of social support in the relation of learned resourcefulness and work stress has a moderating role.

H3c: The “significant other” dimension of social support in the relation of learned resourcefulness and work stress has a moderating role.

The model of the research performed within the framework of the data obtained from the literature and the hypotheses based on them is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model.

Source: prepared by the authors.

According to the research model shown in Figure 1, it is assumed that learned resourcefulness of the employees affect work stress and perceived social support has also a moderating effect. The dependent variable of the research is work stress; the independent variable is learned resourcefulness; the moderating variable between them is perceived social support (family, friend and significant other).

3.1 Instrument

“The Learned Resourcefulness Scale”, developed by Rosenbaum (1980a) and consisted of 36 items to assess employees’ learned resourcefulness levels, was utilized. The Multidimensional Perceived Social Support Scale”, developed by Zimet et al., (1988) to identify hotel employees’ perceived social supports, was used. This scale, composed of 12 items, is collected in three different dimensions as family (3, 4, 8,11), friend (6, 7, 9, 12) and significant other (1, 2, 5, 10). To determine hotel employees’ work stress “The Work Stress Scale”, developed by Cullen et al., (1985) and composed of 6 items, was used.

3.2 Sampling and Data Collection

The population of this study consisted of the employees of four and five-star hotel establishments operating in Cappadocia Region. According to Nevsehir Province Culture and Tourism Directorate, a total of 21 four and five-star hotel establishments exists. As it was not possible to make a full enumeration of research population due to time and cost restrictions of the research, sampling was applied. Judgemental or Purposeful Sampling Method, one of the non random sampling methods, was preferred as the sampling method (Burns & Bush, 2014).

The scales used in order to determine the role of perceived social support on the relation between the hotel establishment employees' learned resourcefulness and work stress were administered to the employees via a questionnaire form.

A total of 500 questionnaire forms were left at the hotels to be able to reach an acceptable sample size however, 390 questionnaire forms were used in this research after the invalid ones were excluded because of the reasons such as not answered completely and with more than one choice ticked.

In the first part of the questionnaire form used in the research, the items assessing the hotel employees' learned resourcefulness, perceived social support and work stress; in the second part demographic questions take part. To measure the items belonging to this scale Likert Type Scale, composed of 5 response categories as "1= I Strongly Disagree", "2= I Disagree", "3 = I am Indecisive", "4= I Agree", "5 = I Strongly Agree".

4 DATA ANALYSIS

A simple and multiple linear regression analysis was performed for the hypotheses tested in the study. Moderating variable points were formed for the future hypotheses and hierarchical regression analysis in which these points were included as predictors was made.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to determine the structural validity of each assessment instrument was carried out within the study scope.

Table 1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Result Diagram of Each Scale.

Scales /Indexes	χ^2/sd	RMSEA	CFI	IFI
Learned Resourcefulness	5.72	0.11	0.88	0.88
Perceived Social Support (Family, Friend and Significant Other)	3.78	0.086	0.98	0.98
Work Stress	21.34	0.23	0.95	0.95

Source: prepared by the authors.

When Table 1 was examined, goodness-of-fit indexes of the model obtained confirmatory factor analysis pertaining to learned resourcefulness scale were examined and it was seen that ($\chi^2/sd=5,72$ $p=0.00$) was significant when proportion of freedom of minimum chi-square value was examined.

However, goodness-of-fit index values were found as RMSEA=0.11, GFI=0.66, CFI=0.88, IFI=0.88. Goodness-of-fit indexes of the model obtained from the consequence of confirmatory factor analysis regarding perceived social support were examined, proportion of freedom of minimal chi-square value was found as $\chi^2/sd=3,78$. And goodness-of-fit index values were found as RMSEA=0.086, GFI=0.92, CFI=0.98, IFI=0.98.

Primarily, all of the 6 items regarding work stress scale were inserted into factor analysis and as a consequence of this, a two dimensional structure emerged. Here, as the 3rd item was under two factors (overlapping), it was omitted from the analysis.

Yet, as work stress scale was studied as one dimensional, with factor fixing method at the consequence of analysis made was fixed to one factor, as the 4th item was loaded with factor value less than 0.5 cut-off value, it was excluded from the analysis and in this study, work stress was measured with 4 items (1, 2, 5, 6). When alpha values of the 4th item concerned were taken into consideration, it was seen to be at a high level (0.863).

In the later analyses made, work stress scale was included in the analyses by being measured with these four items. Goodness-of-fit indexes of the model obtained from the consequence of confirmatory factor analysis related to work stress was examined and the other goodness-of-fit index values belonging to the scales: χ^2/sd rate is calculated as 21.34.

That this rate is ≤ 5 means goodness-of-fit (Kline, 2005; Iqbal, 2020). This value is fairly below the goodness-of-fit criteria. The reason to this is that the number of the items is rather few whereas the sampling size is quite big. Goodness-of-fit index values were found as RMSEA=0.23, GFI=0.90, CFI=0.95, IFI=0.95

Defining statistics, correlations and Cronbach Alpha coefficients related to calculated variables with the purpose of reliability predictions pertaining to the scores obtained at the consequence of the scales' being applied in the study are presented in Table 2.

When Table 2 was examined, it was found that Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient belonging to the total scores taken from learned resourcefulness scale was reliable at medium level and Cronbach alpha internal consistency coefficient belonging to the scores taken from work stress scale was reliable at high level (Özdamar, 2001).

Table 2: Cronbach Alpha Values, Arithmetical Averages, Standard Deviations and Correlation Coefficients.

Variables	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficients						
			1	2	3	4	5	6	
1. LR	3,43	0,36	(0,694)						
2. PSS	3,96	0,82	,478**	(0,923)					
3. PSSIF	4,05	0,90	,480**	,888**	(0,851)				
4. PSSIF	3,93	0,88	,436**	,882**	,693**	(0,818)			
5. PSS/ISO	3,89	1,00	,364**	,895**	,684**	,676**	(0,867)		
6. WS	2,82	0,73	-,352**	-,125*	-,162**	-,136**	-,152**	(0,863)	

** Correlation Coefficient is significant at 0.01 level

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at 0.05 level.

Source: prepared by the authors.

4 FINDINGS

4.1 Demographic Findings

When the gender of the participants is taken into consideration, it is seen that 218 (55.8%) is female; 172 (44.2%) is male. When the marital status is considered, it is seen that 215 (55.2%) out of the participants is single; 175 (44.8%) is married.

When the educational status is considered, it is seen that 72 (18.4%) out of the participants is primary education; 144 (36.9%) is high school; 80 (20.6%) is undergraduate; 65 (16.6%) is graduate; 29 (7.5%) is post graduate. When the work experience of the participants in tourism sector is considered, it is seen that 165 (42.4%) have an experience of 1-5 years; 101 (25.9%) 6-10 years; 87 (22.3%) 11 years and over and 37 (9.4%) less than 1 year.

In addition, it is seen that 192 (49.2%) of the participants have worked in the same organisation for 1-5 years, 128 of them (32.9%) have worked for less than 1 year, 50 of them (12.8%) have worked for 6-10 years and 20 of them (5.1%) have worked for 11 years and over.

4.2 Moderation Analysis

In this study, multiple linear link-state was examined before the analyses were carried out. As the tolerance values are over 0.2 (respectively 0.434, 0.443, 0.454) and VIF values are below 10 (respectively 2.303, 2.258, 2.201), there is not a multiple linear linkage problem. Within the study scope, the results of simple linear regression analysis performed to test H1 are presented in Table 3.

When the analysis results are examined, it is seen that the designed model is significant, $F(1,373)=52.616$, $p<0.05$. There is an inverse relation between independent and dependent variable (0.352). This relation is at medium level. Learned resourcefulness of hotel employees accounts for 12.4 of variation related to work stress.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results Intended for the Effect of Learned Resourcefulness on Work Stress.

Independent Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	β	t	p
Constant	31,530	2,027		15,554	,000
Learned Resourcefulness	-,119	,016	-,352	-7,254	,000

$F_{(1,373)}=52,616$
Significance Level= 0,000
 $R^2=0,124$
Adjusted $R^2=0,348$

Dependent Variable: work stress

Source: prepared by the authors.

According to p values related to regression coefficient significance, learned resourcefulness is a significant variable on work stress. Thus, as learned resourcefulness increases, work stress diminishes. Therefore, H1 is accepted.

Within the study scope, the results of multiple linear regression analysis made to test H2a, H2b and H2c are submitted in Table 4.

Table 4: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results on the Effects of “Family”, “Friend” and “Significant Other” Dimensions of Perceived Social Support on Work Stress.

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	β	t	p	Bivariate	Partial
Constant	20,369	1,110		18,352	,000		
PSS_Family	-,318	,094	-,260	-3,395	,001	-,182	-,174
PSS_Friend	-,134	,095	-,107	-1,412	,159	-,136	-,073
PSS_Significant Other	-,189	,082	-,143	-1,982	,192	-,152	-,091

$F_{(3,371)}=7,308$
Significance Level= 0,000
 $R^2=0,056$
Adjusted $R^2=0,236$

Dependent Variable: work stress

Source: prepared by the authors.

When the analysis results are studied, it is seen that the model designed is significant, $F_{(3,371)}=7.308$, $p<0.05$. The relation between independent and dependent variable is calculated as 0.236. This relation is at low level. The scores the hotel employees get from perceived social support dimensions explain 5.6% of variation related to work stress.

When the bivariate and partial correlations are examined, it is seen that there is a negative relation ($r_{\text{bivariate}}=-0.182$) between “family” and work stress at a low level, when “friend” and “significant other” dimension scores are checked, it is seen that this relation a little lower ($r_{\text{partial}}=-0.174$).

It is seen that there is a negative relation ($r_{\text{bivariate}}=-0.136$) between support taken from “friend” dimension and work stress at a low level when “family” and “significant other” dimension scores are checked, this relation is a bit lower ($r_{\text{partial}}=-0.073$). It is seen that there is a negative ($r_{\text{bivariate}}=-0.152$) relation between the support taken from “significant other” and work stress, when “family” and “friend” support dimension scores are checked, this relation is a little lower ($r_{\text{partial}}=-0.091$).

According to p values regarding the significance of regression coefficient, the scores taken “family” dimension of perceived social support is significant on work stress and although the scores taken “friend” and “significant other” dimensions have a negative relation in bilateral relation, this relation is not significant. Thus, H2a is accepted whereas H2b and H2c are rejected.

The results of hierarchical regression analysis, made to test H3a within the study scope, in which work stress is dependent, learned resourcefulness is independent and “family” dimension of perceived social support is a moderating variable, are presented in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5: Summary of Hierarchical Regression Model Intended to the Moderating Role of “Family” Dimension of Perceived Social Support in the Relation Between Learned Resourcefulness and Work Stress.

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Standard Error of Prediction	Change Statistics				
					Δ R ²	Δ F	sd1	sd2	Δ p
1	,259 ^a	,067	,062	,96853799	,067	13,346	2	372	,000
2	,332 ^b	,110	,103	,94720966	,110	15,283	3	371	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Zscore(Perceived Social Support_Family), Zscore(Learned Resourcefulness)

b. Predictors: (Constant), ZlearnedResourcefulness*ZperceivedSocialSupport_Family, Zscore(Perceived Social Support_Family), Zscore(Learned Resourcefulness)

Source: prepared by the authors.

Summarized information belonging to two models designed in hierarchical analysis takes part in Table 6. The first model covers the variables inserted in regression in the first group (learned resourcefulness as the independent variable and “family” dimension as the moderating variable), whereas the second model entails transactional term (learned resourcefulness and “family” dimension product) regressioned in the second group along with the ones in the first group.

According to R² values in the models, the variables inserted in the first group account for 6.7% of the change in the dependent variable; however, the second model accounts for 11% of the change in the dependent variable with the interactive term inserted. When the analysis results are investigated, it is seen that both of the models constructed are significant ($F_{(2, 372)} = 13.346, p < 0.05$; $F_{(3, 371)} = 15.283, p < 0.05$).

According to the hierarchical regression analysis results presented in Table 6, it was found that learned resourcefulness (B= -0.291, $p < 0.05$) and “family” dimension of perceived social support (B= -0.05, $p < 0.05$) has a significant impact upon work stress. In addition, it was seen that learned resourcefulness and “family” dimension has a significant interactive effect on work stress (B= -0.235, $p < 0.05$).

That the productive result of transactional learned resourcefulness and “family” dimension is significant, indicates that these two variables have an interactive

effect on work stress. According to Aiken & West (1991), the effectiveness size of productive result was measured as $f^2 = 0.04$ and found as a low level (Cohen, 1992). This case indicates that “family” dimension of perceived social support acts as a moderator in the relation between learned resourcefulness and work stress. With this study, H3a was accepted.

Table 6: Hierarchical Regression Analysis on the Moderating Role of “Family” Dimension of Perceived Social Support in the Relationship Between Learned Resourcefulness and Work Stress.

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	B	S.H.	B	S.H.
Learned Resourcefulness	-.287	,060	-.291	,059
Perceived Social Support_Family	,032	,060	-.005	,059
Learned Resourcefulness * Perceived Social Support_Family			-.235	,055
R	,259		,332	
R ²	,061		,110	
Δ R ²	,062		,103	

Source: prepared by the authors.

When the analysis results related to the hypotheses made to specify the moderating role of the perceived social support on the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress and the impact of learned resourcefulness and perceived social support of the employees working in the hotel businesses upon work stress were examined.

It was concluded that “family” dimension, one of the learned resourcefulness and perceived social support dimension, negatively affects work stress and “friend” and “significant other” dimensions, ones of the perceived social support dimensions do not affect work stress.

In addition, it was determined that “family” dimension of perceived social support plays a moderating role in the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Learned resourcefulness is an individual’s ability to use his / her own personal and social sources to be able to cope with problems efficiently. Since face to face communication with clients is dense in hotel businesses, it can be assumed that the individuals with learned resourcefulness manage to solve problems more rapidly (Karakuş et al., 2018).

Besides, the concept of perceived social support which can also be identified as the individual’s feeling

himself / herself valuable by knowing that there are people supporting them when they need help should not be ignored especially in hotel businesses.

Perceived social support enables particularly hotel employees to lead a healthy life, to make more effort for the business, to cope with a challenging situation better and to overcome a stressful situation more easily.

As a study performed by relating the concepts of learned resourcefulness, perceived social support and work stress in hotel businesses with each other is not encountered, this study is thought to contribute to tourism sector.

In the consequence of the analysis made, it was found out that learned resourcefulness affects work stress negatively and therefore, it was concluded and proven with the literature that while hotel employees' learned resourcefulness level increases, their work stress decreases (Rosenbaum, 1980a; Chung et al., 2012; Guloglu, 2017; Ersoy & Ehtiyar, 2021).

When generally considered, individuals use different methods in coping with stress. Individuals are able to cope with stress through various tactics such as seeking social support, using problem solving techniques, having stress management training.

Apart from these techniques, it is emphasized that individuals could cope with stress using their own skills. These skills are called as learned resourcefulness. It can be said that it is not possible to annihilate stress completely; yet, the negative effects of stress and stress sources on individual could be reduced with the increase of learned resourcefulness.

That work stress reduces as perceived social support increases was revealed in the consequences of the analyses performed. Stress causing situations can also be overcome with perceived social support, namely, the conclusion that perceived social support affects work stress negatively is also maintained by the literature (Cobb, 1976; Leung, 2007; Moeller & Chung-Yan, 2013).

In this study, perceived social support is examined in three dimensions, it is concluded that its "family" dimension affects work stress negatively; however, "friend" and "significant other" dimensions have no effect on work stress. According to this result, it can be thought that as hotel businesses are seasonal and workforce speed is fast, hotel employees do not get the support they expect from their counterparts. Factors such as conflict, dispute, rivalry between employees working in busy hotels may cause them to feel more stressed.

In his studies which he performed on organisation culture, Hofstede (1980) emphasized that family is very important. According to him, individuals who are faced with negative situations can recover from their anxiety

with the strength they get from their families.

Nevertheless, individuals take basic values in their work life from their families first. Also people belong to different cultural backgrounds (Mir, 2021) which could affect their life. In the researches of Hofstede (1983), by concluding that Turkish society belongs to communal culture rather than individual and family ties are very strong, it can be said that "family" dimension is more different compared to "friend" and "significant other" dimensions.

In our country, family concepts are valued and family members are highly respected. Hence, that employees working in hotel businesses get support from their families mitigates work stress in working environment and also lessens individual stress. Social supports have different impacts upon individuals and if individuals get the support suitable for them, they could help building the balance of work and family, increasing life satisfaction and leading a less stressful life (Wang et al, 2018). The more support individuals get in work life, the more effort they spend for the business they work in and contribute to that business.

With this study, it was also concluded that "family" dimension of perceived social support plays a moderating role in the relationship between learned resourcefulness and work stress. When "family" dimension of perceived social support is added, the effect of learned resourcefulness on work stress increases.

In line with this conclusion, the effect of learned resourcefulness on work stress emerges both directly and with the support role received from family. Thus, that an individual whose learned resourcefulness is low is supported by the family could help them to be more successful by reducing work stress in work life. Hotel businesses conduct activities aimed at employees' perceived support by developing various human resources practices in order to create a family support atmosphere.

That way, a convenient situation is created for family support emerges. Over time, these supporting activities can be formed into organisation culture and they can be continued. Otherwise, social support perception in employees is not built and it can cause them to feel work stress by influencing their learned resourcefulness negatively.

The studies performed indicate that hotel employees feel more stressful in work life compared to other sector employees and need the stress relieving techniques more (HotelTech Report, 2020). Human factor is fairly important in tourism sector. That an employee who is unhappy and not in a good condition psychologically can not fulfill his / her task to client will lead to client losing with regard to hotel businesses.

Therefore, it is supposed that both employees

and clients can be satisfied by increasing both learned resourcefulness levels of employees (Keskin, 2020) and their getting more support from their families.

In this sense, in order to enable employees to be happier, more peaceful and efficient, hotel businesses may allow employees to be exposed to stress less by improving physical, social and psychological conditions, organizing in service trainings and making their families participate, too, holding sportive activities with families, giving chance employees to be with their families.

Moreover, hotel businesses have the most working hours and shift working system in respect with working hours. Accordingly, shift hours can be shortened by making arrangements in working hours. Hence, the stress levels of employees can also be taken under control.

Just like in many of the studies, this study also has some limitations. Firstly, this one is limited with learned resourcefulness, perceived social support and work stress concepts in hotel businesses. In this study, the moderating role of perceived social support is examined.

In the future studies, related to these variables, the moderating role of perceived social support and the moderating role of learned resourcefulness can also be examined.

Secondly these concepts can be connected with other concepts such as task performance, work control, work-family conflict, psychological pressure, self-esteem wellness, life quality in tourism sector.

Thirdly, by cooperating with hotel administrators, more different studies could also be conducted by developing approaches with solution suggestions about how they increase their learned resourcefulness levels, cope with stress and outcompete with other hotel businesses.

Finally, this study was applied in Cappadocia regions' hotels. Further research in various countries, as well as in different tourism segments, should be conducted to examine if the same results will be yielded.

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APPENDIX

Table 2: Cronbach Alpha Values, Arithmetical Averages, Standard Deviations and Correlation Coefficients.

Variables	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. LR	3,43	0,36	(0,694)					
2. PSS	3,96	0,82	,478**	(0,923)				
3. PSS/ F	4,05	0,90	,480**	,888**	(0,851)			
4. PSS/ F	3,93	0,88	,436**	,882**	,693**	(0,818)		
5. PSS/ SO	3,89	1,00	,364**	,895**	,684**	,676**	(0,867)	
6. WS	2,82	0,73	-,352**	-,125*	-,182**	-,136**	-,152**	(0,863)

** Correlation Coefficient is significant at 0.01 level

*Correlation Coefficient is significant at 0.05 level.

Source: prepared by the authors.

Table 3: Simple Linear Regression Analysis Results Intended for the Effect of Learned Resourcefulness on Work Stress.

Independent Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	β	t	p
Constant	31,530	2,027		15,554	,000
Learned Resourcefulness	-,119	,016	-,352	-7,254	,000

$F_{(1,373)}=52,616$
Significance Level= 0,000
 $R^2=0,124$
Adjusted $R^2=0,348$

Dependent Variable: work stress

Source: prepared by the authors.

Table 4: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results on the Effects of “Family”, “Friend” and “Significant Other” Dimensions of Perceived Social Support on Work Stress.

Independent Variable	Coefficient	Std. Hata	β	t	p	$r_{bivariate}$	$r_{partial}$
Constant	20,369	1,110		18,352	,000		
PSS_Family	-,318	,094	-,260	-3,395	,001	-,182	-,174
PSS_Friend	-,134	,095	-,107	-1,412	,159	-,136	-,073
PSS_Significant Other	-,189	,082	-,143	-1,982	,192	-,152	-,091

$F_{(3,371)}= 7,308$
Significance Level= 0,000
 $R^2=0,056$
Adjusted $R^2= 0,236$

Dependent Variable: work stress

Source: prepared by the authors.

Table 5: Summary of Hierarchical Regression Model Intended to the Moderating Role of “Family” Dimension of Perceived Social Support in the Relation Between Learned Resourcefulness and Work Stress.

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Standard Error of Prediction	Change Statistics				
					ΔR^2	ΔF	sd1	sd2	Δp
1	,259 ^a	,067	,062	,96853799	,067	13,346	2	372	,000
2	,332 ^b	,110	,103	,94720966	,110	15,283	3	371	,000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Zscore(Perceived Social Support_Family), Zscore(Learned Resourcefulness)
b. Predictors: (Constant), ZLearnedResourcefulness*ZPerceived Social Support_Family, Zscore(Perceived Social Support_Family), Zscore(LearnedResourcefulness)

Source: prepared by the authors.

Table 6: Hierarchical Regression Analysis on the Moderating Role of “Family” Dimension of Perceived Social Support in the Relationship Between Learned Resourcefulness and Work Stress.

Variables	Model 1		Model 2	
	B	S.H.	B	S.H.
Learned Resourcefulness	-,287	,060	-,291	,059
Perceived Social Support_Family	,032	,060	-,005	,059
Learned Resourcefulness × Perceived Social Support_Family			-,235	,055
R	,259		,332	
R²	,061		,110	
Δ R²	,062		,103	

Source: prepared by the authors.

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